

Modulatory Effects of *Enantia chlorantha* Stem Bark Extracts on Pancreatic Damage and Hyperglycemia in Streptozotocin-Induced Diabetic Wistar Rats

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Abstract

Natural bioactive compounds targeting pancreatic β -cells have gained increasing attention as potential therapeutic agents for diabetes management. Conventional antidiabetic drugs effectively control hyperglycemia but exhibit limited capacity to restore β -cell function or regeneration and are often associated with adverse effects such as weight fluctuations, hypoglycemia, and gastrointestinal discomfort. This study investigated the protective and restorative effects of hydroethanolic (HEE) and ethyl acetate (EAE) extracts of *Enantia chlorantha* stem bark on pancreatic damage in streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic Wistar rats. Thirty-five rats were randomly assigned to seven groups ($n = 5$). Except for the normal control, all animals received a high-fat diet followed by STZ (35 mg/kg, i.p.) to induce diabetes. Treatments included metformin (50 mg/kg), HEE (200 and 400 mg/kg), and EAE (200 and 400 mg/kg), administered orally for 28 days. The extracts were well tolerated, with no significant effect on final body weight or pancreatic indices ($p > 0.05$). STZ caused mild pancreatic atrophy, whereas extract treatment restored pancreatic mass and architecture in a dose-dependent manner, comparable to metformin. Both HEE and EAE significantly reduced fasting blood glucose on Days 7 and 28, with the 400 mg/kg HEE showing the greatest ameliorative effect. Histopathological analysis confirmed attenuation of STZ-induced pancreatic degeneration. These findings indicate that *E. chlorantha* extracts possess β -cell-protective and regenerative potential, supporting their promise as complementary agents in diabetes management.

Keywords: Diabetes, *Enantia chlorantha*, Histopathology, Pancreas, Streptozotocin

1.0 Introduction

Diabetes mellitus represents a heterogeneous group of metabolic disorders characterized by chronic hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both [1]. The disease manifests primarily in three forms: type 1 diabetes, type 2 diabetes, and gestational diabetes, all of which can occur in individuals of any age and gender [2]. The metabolic derangements associated with diabetes, particularly disturbances in carbohydrate metabolism, become clinically evident when plasma glucose levels rise sufficiently to induce glycosuria and polyuria. These are often accompanied by polydipsia, weight loss, and blurred vision, and in severe cases, untreated hyperglycemia can progress to stupor, coma, or death [3]. While such symptoms are typically absent in the early stages of type 2 diabetes due to

the gradual progression of hyperglycemia, they can be effectively managed through dietary and pharmacological interventions. In contrast, type 1 diabetes usually has an abrupt onset and requires immediate insulin therapy for survival [4]. Chronic hyperglycemia in diabetes is associated with progressive damage and dysfunction in multiple organs, notably the eyes, kidneys, nerves, heart, and blood vessels [5,6]. The acute metabolic emergencies of uncontrolled diabetes include diabetic ketoacidosis and hyperosmolar hyperglycemic syndrome [7]. Long-term complications include diabetic retinopathy, which may result in blindness; nephropathy, leading to renal failure; and peripheral neuropathy, which predisposes patients to foot ulcers, amputations, and Charcot arthropathy. Additionally, autonomic neuropathy can lead to gastrointestinal,

genitourinary, cardiovascular, and sexual dysfunctions [8].

The pathogenesis of diabetes involves complex interactions between genetic, immunological, and environmental factors. In type 1 diabetes, autoimmune destruction of pancreatic β -cells leads to absolute insulin deficiency. Type 2 diabetes, on the other hand, arises from a combination of insulin resistance and relative insulin deficiency due to β -cell dysfunction [9]. The coexistence of defective insulin secretion and impaired insulin action contributes to the characteristic hyperglycemia of diabetes mellitus [10].

Globally, diabetes is a growing public-health burden; the International Diabetes Federation estimates hundreds of millions of adults are living with diabetes and projects a substantial increase by 2030, with the largest relative increase occurring in the African region [11]. Within this region, an estimated 20 million people are currently living with diabetes (approximately 60% of whom remain undiagnosed), and this figure is expected to double to 41.4 million by 2035 [12]. Nigeria bears the highest national burden, with about 3.9 million adults aged 20–79 years living with the condition [13]. Although diabetes has historically been considered an adult-onset disease, recent trends indicate a disturbing rise in pediatric and adolescent cases. This shift is closely linked to rapid urbanization, lifestyle transitions, and the increasing adoption of Western dietary habits across Africa. The move towards highly processed, calorie-dense foods rich in fat, sugar, and salt, coupled with physical inactivity, has markedly increased the prevalence of obesity and metabolic disorders in African cities [14]. Conversely, rural communities continue to face nutritional deficiencies primarily due to poverty, conflict, and environmental constraints rather than cultural practices. In these areas, food insecurity and inequitable distribution of local staples such as sorghum, millet, maize, yams, and plantain exacerbate health disparities [14].

The management of diabetes involves a multifaceted approach aimed at maintaining normoglycemia and preventing complications. Conventional therapeutic strategies include reducing insulin demand, stimulating endogenous insulin secretion, enhancing insulin sensitivity in target tissues, and inhibiting carbohydrate-degrading enzymes [15]. Among oral hypoglycemic agents, metformin, a biguanide derivative, remains the first-line pharmacological choice for type 2 diabetes. Its principal mechanism involves suppression of hepatic gluconeogenesis, delaying

intestinal glucose absorption, promoting non-oxidative glucose disposal in skeletal muscles, and enhancing insulin-mediated glucose uptake in peripheral tissues, thus collectively reducing plasma glucose levels with minimal risk of hypoglycemia [16]. However, despite its efficacy, metformin and other synthetic antidiabetic agents are associated with several drawbacks, including non-specific action, potential toxicity, and gastrointestinal side effects such as bloating, diarrhea, abdominal discomfort, and flatulence [16]. Moreover, these agents often fail to prevent or reverse secondary diabetic complications. Consequently, there is an increasing demand for safer, cost-effective, and accessible alternatives [17].

Medicinal plants have gained renewed interest as potential sources of bioactive compounds for the management of diabetes. Approximately 80% of the world's population relies on plant-based traditional medicines for primary healthcare needs [18]. Numerous studies have demonstrated that phytotherapeutic agents can effectively modulate glucose metabolism with fewer adverse effects compared to synthetic drugs. These plants are known to contain bioactive constituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, phenolics, and glycosides, which contribute to their antidiabetic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties [3,5,6,7,9].

Enantia chlorantha, commonly known as African yellow wood, belongs to the family Annonaceae and is widely distributed across the tropical rainforests of West and Central Africa [19]. In Nigeria, it is known by various local names, including *Awogba* or *Osu pupa* (Yoruba), *Dokitaigbo* (Southeast Nigeria), *Kakerim* (Boki, Cross River State), and *Erenba-vbogo* (Benin) [20]. The plant has long been valued in African traditional medicine for the treatment of diverse ailments such as malaria, jaundice, hepatitis, ulcers, and infections [21]. The stem bark is the most used part, often prepared as decoctions, tinctures, or infusions, and consumed as herbal drinks (*agbo*) or powders (*agunmu*) [22]. Phytochemical analyses have identified numerous bioactive constituents in *Elantra. Chlorantha*, including alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, phenols, reducing sugars, and cardiac glycosides, with alkaloids present in the highest concentration [23,24]. These compounds are believed to underlie its pharmacological properties such as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimalarial activities [25,26]. Traditional uses of *Enantia. Chlorantha* across Africa includes treatments for malaria, hepatitis, jaundice, tuberculosis, typhoid fever, and

gastrointestinal disorders [28,29]. In Nigeria and Cameroon, the bark decoction is used for liver diseases, urinary tract infections, and ulcers, while infusions are applied for wound healing and cough relief [30]. Given its rich phytochemical composition and broad ethnomedicinal applications, *Enantia chlorantha* has emerged as a promising candidate for antidiabetic research. Investigating its potential to modulate glucose metabolism and restore pancreatic function could provide valuable insights into plant-based alternatives for diabetes management.

2.0 Materials and Methods

All solvents and reagents used were of analytical grade. Ethyl acetate (EtOAc, $\geq 99.5\%$) and Ethanol (absolute, $\geq 99.8\%$) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Distilled water was used throughout the study. All other chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade and obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany) and used without further purification.

2.1 Plant material collection and identification

Fresh plant material (stem bark) of *Elantra chlorantha* was collected from an open forest in Irrua, Esan-Central Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria, in March 2025. The plant was identified and authenticated at the Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, University of Benin, Nigeria. A voucher specimen (No. UBH-E485) was prepared and deposited in the Herbarium section of the department for reference. The collected material was washed to remove debris and air-dried under shade at room temperature ($25\text{--}28\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) until constant weight. The dried material was pulverized into fine powder using a stainless-steel grinder, Thomas / Thomas Scientific (Wiley Mill Model 4), and stored in airtight amber containers at $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until further analysis.

2.1.1. Preparation of hydroethanolic extract (HEE)

One hundred grams (100 g) of the powdered plant material was extracted with 1 L of 70% ethanol (ethanol:water, 70:30 v/v; solid-solvent ratio 1:10, w/v) by cold maceration at room temperature ($25 \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 72 h with intermittent shaking. The mixture was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, and the residue was re-extracted with an additional 100 mL of the same solvent to ensure exhaustive extraction. The combined filtrates were concentrated under reduced pressure at $40\text{--}45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

using a rotary evaporator (Büchi Rotavapor R-210, Switzerland) to obtain the crude hydroethanolic extract. The extract was subsequently freeze-dried and stored in a refrigerator at $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until required for use.

Percent yield of the extract was calculated using equation 1.

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weights of solvent free extract (g)} \times 100}{\text{Dried extract weight (g)}} \quad (1)$$

2.1.2. Preparation of Ethyl acetate Extract (EAE)

One hundred grams (100 g) of the powdered plant material was extracted with 1 L of ethyl acetate (solid-solvent ratio 1:10, w/v) by cold maceration at room temperature ($25 \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 72 h with intermittent shaking. The mixture was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, and the residue was re-extracted with an additional 100 mL of the same solvent to ensure complete extraction. The combined filtrates were concentrated under reduced pressure at $40\text{--}45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ using a rotary evaporator (Büchi Rotavapor R-210, Switzerland) to obtain the crude ethyl acetate extract. The concentrated extract was subsequently freeze-dried and stored in a refrigerator at $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until required for use.

Percent yield of the extract was calculated using equation 2.

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weights of solvent free extract (g)} \times 100}{\text{Dried extract weight (g)}} \quad (2)$$

2.2 Source of experimental animals and management

Thirty-six (36) male Wistar rats (8 weeks old) weighing between 180g – 200g (mean weight = 190 ± 10) were obtained from the Animal House, Biochemistry Department, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria, in March 2025. The animals were housed in standard polypropylene cages under controlled environmental conditions (temperature $25 \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; 12 h light/12 h dark cycle) and fed with standard laboratory chow and water *ad libitum*. Animals were allowed to acclimatize for two weeks before the commencement of the experiment. All animal procedures complied with the National Research Council guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals [25] and were approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria,

with an approval reference number (FLSRE-2023-018).

2.3 Acute Toxicity Test of HEE and EAE of *Enantia chlorantha* Stem Bark

The acute oral toxicity of the hydroethanolic and ethyl acetate extracts were assessed following the method described by Lorke [31]. In the first phase, nine rats were divided into three groups (n = 3) and administered the extract orally at doses of 10, 100, and 1000 mg/kg body weight. In the second phase, three rats received 1600, 2900, and 5000 mg/kg body weight, respectively. All animals were observed continuously for the first 4 h, intermittently for 24 h, and daily for 14 days for signs of toxicity or mortality.

2.4 Diet Formulation

Both the high-fat diet and the normal diet (HFD and ND, respectively) were prepared. The content of the high-fat diet included corn starch from a carbohydrate source, fish meal from a protein source, soybean oil from fat and oils, butter from fat and oils, sucrose from a simple sugar, cellulose from a fiber source, vitamin mix from vitamins, and mineral mix from minerals (Table 1). The normal diet contained all the constituents of the high-fat diet except for butter (Table 2). The cornstarch was dried for 3 days consecutively before the formulation of the feed. After the drying process, the contents of the high-fat diet and the normal diet were measured; using this measurement, these contents were mixed and pelleted. It was left to dry for a few hours.

Table 1: Composition of the constituents in High-fat diet

Raw materials	Source	Amount (g)
Corn starch	Carbohydrate	5,125.0
Cellulose	Fiber	625.00
Sucrose	Simple sugar	1,250.00
Fish meal	Protein	1,750.00
Soybean oil	Fats and oil	500.00
Mineral mix	Mineral	437.50
Vitamin mix	Vitamin	125.00
Butter	Fats and oil	2,687.50

Table 2: Composition of the constituents in Normal Diet.

Raw materials	Source	Amount (g)
Cornstarch	Carbohydrate	2,562.50
Cellulose	Fiber	875.00
Sucrose	Simple sugar	625.00
Fish meal	Protein	312.50
Soybean oil	Fat and oil	250.00
Mineral mix	Minerals	62.50
Vitamin mix	Vitamins	218.75

2.5 Experimental Design

The rats were randomly distributed into seven groups as follows:

Group 1: This is the normal control; they were fed with a normal diet only for four weeks throughout the duration of the study.

Group 2: This is the diabetic control; the rats were fed with a high-fat diet for four weeks. They were induced with a single dose of streptozotocin (35 mg/kg body weight), and no treatment of any kind was given throughout the duration of the study.

Group 3: This is the positive control; Rats were fed with a high-fat diet for four weeks and were induced with a single dose of streptozotocin (35 mg/kg body weight) and then treated with the administration of the standard antidiabetic drug, Metformin (50 mg/kg body weight), daily for the duration of the study.

Group 4: Rats were fed with a high-fat diet for four weeks and were induced with a single dose of streptozotocin (35 mg/kg body weight) and then treated with the administration of 200 mg/kg of the HEE daily for the duration of the study.

Group 5: Rats were fed with a high-fat diet for four weeks and were induced with a single dose of streptozotocin (35 mg/kg body weight) and then treated with the administration of 400 mg/kg of the HEE daily for the duration of the study.

Group 6: Rats were fed with a high-fat diet for four weeks and were induced with a single dose of streptozotocin (35 mg/kg body weight) and then treated with the administration of 200 mg/kg of the EAE daily for the duration of the study.

Group 7: Rats were fed with a high-fat diet for four weeks and were induced with a single dose of streptozotocin (35 mg/kg body weight) and then

treated with the administration of 400 mg/kg of the EAE daily for the duration of the study

2.5.1 Induction of Diabetes and Administration of Extracts

Diabetes mellitus was induced in the test groups after an overnight fast by a one-time intraperitoneal injection of streptozotocin (50 mg/kg body weight) dissolved in 0.1 M cold citrate buffer (pH 4.5). Fasting blood glucose levels were checked after 72 hours. Rats with fasting blood glucose ≥ 200 mg/dL were considered diabetic [32]. Fasting blood glucose (FBG) levels were determined with the aid of ACCU-CHEK Advantage II Active Glucometer (Roche, Germany). The test strip was inserted into the glucometer; a blood sample was collected from the rat's tail by tail tipping using a surgical blade. The blood was dropped on the dextrostix reagent pad. This was inserted into a microprocessor digital blood glucometer, and the readings were recorded in mg/dL.

2.5.2 Tissue Collection and Preservation

At the end of the study period, following an overnight fast, all rats were weighed, and fasting blood glucose levels were measured and recorded. Thereafter, the animals were anesthetized with an intraperitoneal injection of urethane at a dose of 1.5 g/kg body weight, as previously described by Bilanda et al [33] and reported by Osagie-Eweka and Orhue [34]. Upon confirmation of deep anesthesia, each rat was placed in a supine position and carefully inverted. A midline incision was made through the abdominal wall to open the peritoneal cavity, which was extended toward the thoracic region using a sterile dissecting blade. The pancreas was excised, rinsed gently in normal saline to remove adherent blood, and immediately fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for subsequent histological analysis.

2.6 Histopathological study

The harvested pancreases were rinsed in normal saline, soaked in 10% formalin for 12 hours, and then prepared according to the paraffin wax embedding technique, followed by staining with hematoxylin and eosin for microscopic evaluation. Histopathological examination was carried out under a light microscope, examined, and photomicrography was performed (magnification x400). In each H&E section, exactly 25 circular tubules were measured in two axes drawn perpendicularly to each other with the aid of an image analyzer (Image Proplus, version 3.0).

2.7 Statistical analysis

All quantitative data were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism version 9.0 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA). Data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's post-hoc test for multiple comparisons. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3.0 Results

3.1. Acute Toxicity Test of HEE and EAE of *Enantia chlorantha*

The treated rats did not show any toxicity signs and symptoms at the highest dose of 5000 mg/kg bw, and the HEE and EAE of *Enantia chlorantha* stem bark did not produce any rat mortality in both phases 1 and 2 acute toxicity tests (Tables 3 and 4).

Table 3: Phases 1 and 2 Acute Toxicity Test of Hydro Ethanol Extract (HEE) of *Enantia chlorantha*

Dose (mg/kg body weight)	Phase 1 mortality	Phase 2 mortality
10	0/3	-
100	0/3	-
1000	0/3	-
1500	-	0/3
2500	-	0/3
5000	-	0/3

Table 4: Phases 1 and 2 Acute Toxicity Test of Ethyl Acetate Extract (EAE) of *Enantia chlorantha*

Dose (mg/kg body weight)	Phase 1 mortality	Phase 2 mortality
10	0/3	-
100	0/3	-
1000	0/3	-
1500	-	0/3
2500	-	0/3
5000	-	0/3

3.2. Effect of Graded Doses of HEE and EAE of *Enantia chlorantha* Stem Bark on Rat Body Weight

The impact of the HEE and EAE of *Enantia chlorantha* on body weight changes in streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic rats is presented in Table 5. There were increases in the body weights of the Wistar rats across the groups.

Groups 5 and 7 had a significantly increased weight gain when compared to the normal control and diabetic control. All treatment groups maintained normal feeding behavior and activity throughout the study period. The final body weights of the extract-treated groups showed no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) compared with the normal control, indicating that the extracts had no adverse effect on overall growth or nutritional status. Pancreatic

weight and relative organ weight remained within the physiological range (0.35–0.45% of body weight). The STZ-treated group exhibited a slight reduction in pancreatic mass compared with controls, while administration of *Enantia chlorantha* extracts (both hydroethanol and Ethyl acetate) produced a modest normalization of pancreatic weight, comparable to that observed in the metformin-treated group.

Table 5: Body weight and pancreatic weight of control and rats treated with *Elantra chlorantha* extracts

Group	Initial Body Weight (g)	Final Body Weight (g)	Pancreas Weight (g)	Relative Organ Weight (%)
Group 1 (Normal control)	184.2 ± 6.5	195.2 ± 5.6	0.86±0.06	0.44±0.02
Group 2 (35 mg/kg bw STZ)	186.5±7.1	188.4±4.8 ^a	0.63±0.05 ^a	0.33±0.02 ^a
Group 3 (200 mg/kg bw Metformin)	183.5±5.9	197.1±5.2 ^b	0.81±0.05	0.41±0.02
Group 4 (200 mg/kg bw HEE)	182.6±2.7	194.9±5.5	0.78±0.02	0.40±0.01
Group 5 (400 mg/kg bw HEE)	185.2±6.9	198.7±2.3 ^b	0.84±0.02	0.42±0.02
Group 6 (200 mg/kg bw EAE)	184.1±6.4	196.2±3.1 ^b	0.76±0.04	0.39±0.01
Group 7 (400 mg/kg bw EAE)	187.4±6.8	199.6±7.0 ^b	0.84±0.05	0.42±0.02

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM (n=3). Values with superscript ^a are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from the normal control group, while values with superscript ^b are significantly different from the diabetic control group.

3.3 Antidiabetic Effects of *Enantia Chlorantha* Stem Bark Extracts in STZ-induced diabetic rats

The antidiabetic activity of extracts of *Enantia Chlorantha* stem bark in the diabetes model is shown in Table 6. The rats induced with diabetes showed a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in blood glucose level, when compared with the normal control group on Day 3. Meanwhile, there was a

dose-dependent reduction in blood glucose levels in the diabetic treated rats on Days 7 and 29 when compared to diabetic control. With hydroethanol extract having greater amelioration at the higher dose of 400mg/kg body weight, similarly, administration of the standard drug, metformin, significantly lowers the increased glucose levels throughout the experiment.

Table 6: Fasting blood glucose levels of control rats and diabetic rats treated with stem back extracts of *Enantia chlorantha*

Group/dose	Fasting blood glucose level (mg/dl)			
	Day 0	Day 3	Day 14	Day 29
Group 1 (Normal control)	78.00 ± 2.06	69.00 ± 2.66	95.00 ± 2.06	83.61 ± 2.09
Group 2 (35mg/kg bw STZ)	86.02 ± 1.19 ^a	295.50 ± 1.46 ^a	447.00 ± 7.04 ^a	452.00 ± 7.80 ^a
Group 3 (STZ + 200mg/kg bw Metformin)	77.50 ± 0.84 ^b	355.00 ± 4.90 ^b	105.50 ± 1.46 ^b	86.5.80 ± 1.44 ^b
Group 4 (STZ + 200mg/kg bw HEE)	80.00 ± 1.19 ^b	353.00 ± 3.36 ^b	123.00 ± 2.06 ^b	95.00 ± 3.76 ^b
Group 5 (STZ + 400mg/kg bw HEE)	78.00 ± 1.18 ^b	313.50 ± 1.46 ^b	109.5 ± 6.00 ^b	97.00 ± 3.14 ^b
Group 6 (STZ + 200mg/kg bw EAE)	80.5 ± 1.46 ^b	317.5 ± 0.84 ^b	126.50 ± 0.84 ^b	90.5 ± 4.03 ^b
Group 7 (STZ + 400mg/kg bw EAE)	82.50 ± 1.85 ^b	351.50 ± 0.84 ^b	123.00 ± 4.44 ^b	81.5 ± 2.22 ^b

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n =3). Values with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from one another. ^amean is significant ($p < 0.05$) when compared with the normal control. ^b mean is significant ($p < 0.05$) when compared with diabetic control group.

3.4 Histopathology

The photomicrographs of the pancreas (plates 1-7) show the relationship between streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats and the dose administration of standard antidiabetic drug, metformin, hydroethanol extract, and ethyl acetate extract of *Enantia*

chlorantha stem bark. Streptozotocin caused acinar degeneration and inflammatory infiltration. Extract-treated groups showed marked histological recovery, most pronounced in the hydroethanol group.

Plate 1: Group 1 (Normal Control). Composed of **A:** Interlobar ducts. **B:** Islets of Langerhans. **C:** exocrine acinar (H&E x 400). Cells of the pancreas were all present in their normal proportions. The islets cells are seen embedded

Plate 2: Diabetic control where rats were given STZ only. **A:** normal acinar. **B:** Atrophied Islets of Langerhans. **C:** Ulcerated interlobar arteries (H&E x 400). Islets are nonexistent due to the cytotoxic (selective toxicity) mechanism of STZ on β -cells.

Plate 3: Rats were given STZ and treated with 200 mg/kg bw of Metformin, showing **A:** Normal acinar. **B:** normal Islets of Langerhans. **C:** Vascular ulceration (H&E x 400).

Plate 4: Rat given STZ + 200 mg/kg bw of hydroethanol extract showing **A:** hypotrophied islets of Langerhans. **B:** normal acinar. **C:** ulcerated interlobar vessels (H&E x 400).

Plate 5: Rat given STZ + 400 mg/kg bw of hydroethanol Extract showing **A:** Normal exocrine acinar. **B:** Normal Islets of Langerhans. **C:** Vascular stenosis (H&E x 400).

Plate 6: Rat given STZ + 200 mg/kg bw Ethylacetate Extract showing **A:** luxuriant Islets of Langerhans. **B:** Normal exocrine acinar. **C:** normal vascular architecture (H&E x 400)

Plate 7: Rat given STZ + 400 mg/kg bw Ethylacetate Extract showing **A:** Normal exocrine acinar **B:** Atrophied Islets of Langerhans (H&E x 400).

4.0 Discussion

Diabetes mellitus is one of the most common systemic diseases in the world, and it occurs due to an absolute deficiency of insulin production and secretion by the β -cells of the pancreatic islets of Langerhans. However, in many types of diabetes mellitus, hyperglycaemia (elevation of blood glucose concentration) is a common effect of

uncontrolled diabetes, and over time, this leads to damage, dysfunction, and failure of many of the body's organs, including the pancreas [35]. Many of the islets of Langerhans cells are formed by β cells, which are responsible for producing insulin. Depletion of the β cells will therefore result in insulin deficiency, which leads to disorders in carbohydrate, protein, and fat metabolism with resultant hyperglycemia [36].

The pancreatic β cells were destroyed by streptozotocin because it is a selective toxicant for pancreatic β cells [37]. This led to the development of hyperglycemia and, subsequently, diabetes.

Metformin, a biguanide marketed under the trade name Glucophage among others, is the first line commonly used antidiabetic drug that is involved in the stimulation of glucose uptake in the tissue and the increase of glucose removal in the blood [38]. The glucose-lowering activity exhibited by *Enantia chlorantha* extracts could be due to the ability of the extracts to inhibit endogenous glucose production, inhibit insulinase, or increase insulin production from the β -cells of the pancreas [39]. Many medicinal plants known to be effective against several diseases have also been shown to be toxic at certain doses with prolonged exposure [40]. The acute toxicity study of the HEE and EAE of *Enantia chlorantha* stem bark showed it possesses no toxic effects since no adverse reactions or mortalities were observed in the rats that were administered low to high doses of the HEE and EAE. This observation suggests a high tolerance and safety level of the extracts. This can be attributed to the extract lacking toxic constituents that could trigger adverse reactions at the tested doses. It can also imply that the leaves are relatively safe for human and animal consumption, although there is no data yet on chronic toxicity tests.

Changes in body weight serve as a sensitive indicator of the general health status of animals. Weight loss is often synonymous with loss of appetite due to disturbances in carbohydrate, protein, or fat metabolism [41]. Streptozotocin significantly reduced pancreatic weight and relative organ weight. *Enantia chlorantha* extracts restored values toward normal, ethyl acetate extract showing near-normal parameters

Histological study of the diabetic control (plate 2) rats, when compared to the normal control (plate 1), showed degeneration of the pancreatic islets of Langerhans cells due to the cytotoxic streptozotocin used in this study. This gave rise to insulin deficiency, hence diabetes in the rats. In the result of diabetic-treated groups after administration of standard antidiabetic drug, metformin, and extract fractions of *Enantia chlorantha* revealed an increase in insulin secretion from surviving β cells of the islets of Langerhans. The positive control (plate 3) revealed that the islets of Langerhans were gradually regenerated after being treated with 50mg/kg body weight of Metformin, when compared to the diabetic control, where the islets were atrophied. This agrees with the findings of

Eliakim and Obri [42] as well as with Ojeaburu and Eimoga [43].

Enantia chlorantha stem bark hydroethanol extract of 200mg/kg body weight (plate 4) revealed hypertrophied islets of Langerhans, but when there was an increase in the dose to 400mg/kg body weight (plate 5), the B cells of the islets of Langerhans were gradually recovering from the damage done by streptozotocin. This implies that the effect of the hydroethanol extract of *Enantia chlorantha* on damaged pancreatic cells is dose-dependent. Ethyl acetate extract of *Enantia chlorantha* in a low dose of 200mg/kg body weight (plate 6) expressed tremendous regeneration and increment in the number of islets of Langerhans compared to the normal and diabetic controls. The β cells were recovered for the secretion of insulin, but when a high dose of ethyl acetate, 400mg/kg body weight (plate 7), was administered, it was observed that this dose was inefficient for the islets of Langerhans; hence, they remained atrophied, and there was insulin deficiency in the rats. This aligns with the findings of Edem [39].

The antidiabetic efficacy of ethyl acetate extract of *Enantia chlorantha* in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats worked better in the regeneration and recovery of β -cells of islets of Langerhans than in metformin.

5.0 Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that the administration of a low dose of ethyl acetate extract of *Enantia chlorantha* in pancreatic cells (β -cells) repairs damaged islets caused by streptozotocin and treats the deficiency of insulin secretion in diabetic rats. Hence, this study shows that *Enantia chlorantha* stem bark extracts exert significant antidiabetic effects on diabetic rats and can be employed in the treatment/management of diabetes mellitus at the right dose. An understanding of the changes that occur at the level of the pancreas has the potential to lead to dramatic changes in this unacceptable situation. While the pancreas may play a central role in diabetes pathogenesis, all research-derived observations must be considered in the context of the body's entirety, which includes the circulatory network and many organ systems that may not be reproducible in an experimental context. We remain optimistic that advances in pancreatic research will lead to improvements in disease diagnosis, understanding of disease heterogeneity and optimization of treatments at a personalized level.

Further research is warranted to explore the underlying mechanisms, isolate active constituents, and assess long-term efficacy and safety. Continued investigation into this medicinal plant may yield valuable insights into the development of novel antidiabetic therapies.

6.0 Recommendations

1. Phytochemical isolation and characterization: Future research should focus on isolating and identifying the specific bioactive compounds responsible for the observed pancreatic protection, with emphasis on flavonoid and lignan derivatives.

2. Mechanistic and molecular studies: Further investigations using molecular assays are recommended to elucidate the precise mechanisms of action, including modulation of oxidative stress pathways (e.g., Nrf2, NF- κ B) and apoptotic signaling in pancreatic tissues.

3. Dose optimization and safety evaluation: Sub-chronic and chronic toxicity studies are necessary to establish the safety margins and therapeutic index of the extracts, ensuring their suitability for potential clinical use.

4. Comparative solvent studies: A broader range of solvent systems (e.g., methanol, aqueous, or butanol fractions) should be evaluated to determine the solvent that yields the optimal bioactive profile for pancreatic protection.

5. Translational and diabetic models: It is recommended that subsequent studies assess the efficacy of *Enantia chlorantha* extracts in experimental models of diabetes or pancreatitis to explore their potential role in glucose metabolism and pancreatic regeneration.

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